

Inspire & desire

Pieter M.A. Desmet, Department of Industrial Design, Delft University of Technology - The Netherlands

Abstract

This paper discusses two pleasant emotions that are considered to be eminent responses in the domain of product design: inspire and desire. To explore their underlying eliciting conditions a study was performed in which participants collected pictures of products that elicit either inspiration or desire. On the basis of these cases three types of product inspiration and three types of product desire are proposed. Inspiring products are reported to infuse participants with creativity. In those cases we are stimulated to have new thoughts, or ideas, or initiate some activity or behaviour. In other cases inspiration illumination is manifested in a renewed sense of some loved facet of one's identity. In the third type of inspiration illumination takes the form of a shift in perspective. Some products uplift us from the realm of ordinary thoughts and feelings of every day life. These three types of inspiration are similar in terms of experience but somewhat different in terms of eliciting conditions. A similar structure is proposed for desire. Desire of consequence refers to those instances in which desire is elicited by anticipated consequences of (owning or using) the product. Desire of presence is the desire to retain sensory delight that some products may provide us with, and desire for identity is evoked by a personal identification with or resonance with a product. The distinctions between the different types of inspiration and desire are thought to be valuable for design research and practice because they focus on the conditions that elicit emotions, and insights in these conditions are applicable in new design efforts.

Keywords: Pleasant emotions; appraisal; inspiration; desire; eliciting conditions; photo study.

Introduction

Emotion research in psychology is predominantly focused on those emotions that are considered to be negative or *unpleasant*. Typologies of basic emotions typically include only one pleasant emotion for three up to five unpleasant, and the nature of included pleasant emotions is very general, such as ‘happiness.’ For design research this focus is not satisfying because designers mostly aim to create products that evoke *pleasant* responses. And although it is relevant to have insights in how and when products elicit unpleasant emotions, for design practice insights in how products elicit pleasant emotions are especially helpful. The current paper discusses two emotions that, although scarcely discussed in psychologist literature, are considered to be eminent for product design: inspiration and desire. It was decided to investigate specifically these two because they are prominent experiences and because their eliciting conditions cannot be explained with current appraisal theory (see Desmet, 2002).

The conditions that underlie these two emotions in the domain of product design are explored with a ‘research through design’ approach. First a study was performed in which participants were instructed to take pictures of products in their daily surroundings that elicit particular emotions. In a little note book they explained why these particular products elicited these emotions. Second, a design workshop was organised in which twelve design students examined these conditions from a designer’s point of view. The conditions that underlie inspiration and desire are discussed, and example cases drawn from the photo study are quoted to reflect the diversity of the participants’ narrative descriptions. The discussed conditions are thought to be valuable for design research and practice because insights in these conditions are applicable in new design efforts. In a general discussion, we reflect on the value of focussing on distinct emotions rather than on generalised pleasant responses (such as pleasure or enjoyment).

Approach

Twenty-nine Dutch people, aged between 25 and 36, participated in a photo study. All participants volunteered and were not paid. All participants were provided with a photo-film and a booklet that contained 21 pages. On the first page, a set of ten emotions was printed. The remaining 20 pages provided space for the participant’s rationales (each page for comments on a single photo). The goal and procedure of the task were explained in a written

introduction. Participants were instructed to photograph (at least) 10 products, each one of which elicited one of the given emotions. These ten emotions had been randomly picked from a total set of 14 emotions relevant for product experience assembled by Desmet (2002). In the notebook participants recorded for each case the product, the emotion, and why that emotion was experienced. They were instructed to formulate their explanation as detailed as possible, and invited to describe whatever they thought was relevant to explain their emotion (e.g. context, product design, and associations). The task was performed in a period of six weeks. Each participant submitted between 10 and 15 cases, resulting in an anecdotal database of 383 cases. Each case includes a picture of a product, a participant number, an emotion, a description of the underlying appraisal. Of these cases only those that refer to inspiration (29 cases) and to desire (31 cases) are discussed in the current paper. We did not use a particular template or strategy to assess and organise the data, but searched for patterns including the phenomenology of the event, commonalities and diversities in our data, triggers or context, meaning to the person, variety, and anything else that seemed relevant. Although there was certainly diversity in the material, the cases revealed a high degree of consistency in underlying conditions. In the next stage of the project, 12 design students (Master DFI of Delft University) discussed the applicability of these conditions in conceptual design activities.

Inspiration

In ancient inspired creativity, the Muses have been described as whispering, breathing, or singing into the recipient. This view corresponds with the etymological origin for inspiration, the Latin 'inspire', which means something like 'to breathe into, to inflame.' Also in modern literature, inspiration is commonly associated with creative processes (see, for example, Williams, 1982) and seen as the moment of discovery that constitutes a breakthrough in the way we have been thinking about a problem (see May, 1975). In that line of thought, Arieti (1976) suggests that inspiration occurs at the moment of finding a means to translate a creative idea into form. This traditional view on inspiration can be applied to any creative process, whether it is an artist creating a composition, a cosmetic surgeon (re)sculpturing a face, or a chef developing a new technique to prepare asparagus. Note that, besides in the realm of creativity, inspiration is also frequently discussed in accounts of mysticism and religion to articulate spiritual awakening or sacred revelation. Though fascinating, none of these accounts seem to acknowledge the role of inspiration in our ordinary day-to-day

experiences. Surely, many products associated with inspiration are used in activities that are creative (e.g. paint brushes and musical instruments), religious (e.g. rosaries and the Ka'ba), or spiritual (meditation pillows and talismans), but I prefer to regard these products as representing rather than eliciting inspiration. Although this distinction may be somewhat ambiguous (think, for example, of one who is inspired by a magical gem because it represents an inspirational value), the current investigation focuses specifically on instances in which the product elicits (and not represents) the experience of inspire.

Antecedents of inspiration

Although the collected examples show substantial variation in participants' explanation of why and how products elicit inspiration, the eliciting conditions show two main ingredients: *illumination* and *connection* (see also Hart, 1998). The first refers to the experience of a heightened state of awareness. All inspiring products initiate a shift in perspective, an experience of a deeper meaning or clarity, or a grasping of unexpected associations. The second variable refers to a perceived altering of one's personal boundaries to include some external object. In some cases this external object can be the product itself, and in other cases the object is something that is represented by or associated with the product, like the self, an idea, or someone else. The cases indicate three variations in the way illumination and connection can be manifested in the experience of product inspiration.

Inspiration into form

Inspiration that manifests into form corresponds with the traditional view in which inspiration is conceived as the moment of illumination in a creative process. Fourteen examples report of products that infused participants with new and creative thoughts or ideas. Users report "ideas start bubbling," "my head starts working," "I feel creative," etcetera. One person describes the experience of inspiration when looking at a particular chair: "This chair holds many interesting elements. It has simple yet complex shapes, an interesting inside-outside relationship; it suggest a personally, and it has sensual shapes. This inspires me because it functions as the starting point for my own thoughts and ideas." These cases can be described as a 'light bulb' of an idea popping up. One person was inspired by a book to enrol in a mountain climbing course, and another was inspired by a tablecloth to make her own napkins. This type of inspiration is illumination that is manifested in sensing a possibility that opens the doors to new actions or thoughts.

Inspiration into being

Inspiration can also manifest into a (renewed) sense of the self. People can be inspired by objects that represent essential values or self-images. One person describes the inspiration elicited by a horse saddle: “sometimes life can be very stressful and I tend to forget who I am and what is important to me. Whenever I see a horse saddle, I am inspired because it reminds me of my love for riding: taking time to relax, being in contact with the horse, with nature.” In these ten cases, the illumination manifests into a renewed sense of some part of the self or identity (e.g. hobbies, field of expertises, skills, passions, or values). One person reports being inspired by a cooking pan because it reminds him of his passion for cooking, and another person was inspired by a pair of shoes because whenever she wears them she feels in contact with her femininity. In these cases the inspiration is not related to creativity but to a new or renewed connection with the self.

Inspiration into awareness

A third manifestation of inspiration is into a general state of awareness. Some people report how inspirational products enabled them to see a kind of hidden layer or order in reality. Others explain how products shed new light on some old belief. One person submitted a picture of an electric iron that inspired him because the heat, steam, and danger exhibited the basic elements of energy and he suddenly realised the complexity that of seemingly simple processes. Other people give examples of inspiration that is manifested in an experience of extraordinary unity and clarity. One person describes how he is inspired by a watch: “I am inspired by this watch because the output is very simple a straightforward – the time, while at the same time, the internal mechanism is very complex. This tension field between complexity and simplicity represents an always-returning theme of life.” This inspiration is associated with an awareness of the whole and a general sense of fulfilment.

Desire

Apple’s introduction of the iPod has been a blessing for many design lecturers because it proved to be the perfect example to illustrate the value of proper design. This modern classic demonstrates that plastic can be beautiful, that smart technology can be intuitive in use, and foremost, that mass produced products can be *desirable*. Desire is generally seen as involuntary and passionate, as something that we do not control but controls us. In the realm of product design we associate desire with an irrational hunger, yearning, or craving for some

object, a suspicious emotion that lures us into buying things we may not be able to afford or may not even have a function for. Given the strong behavioural impact, it makes sense that especially consumer researchers have shown an interest in this emotion. Lynn and Harris (1997), for example, gave an account of the desire for unique consumer products, Ger et al. (1993) discussed the development of consumer desire in developing economies, and Meister (1996) gave an elaborate account of the role of desire in socialism versus capitalism. The focus in consumer research is always on behavioural phenomena associated with desire; either on a personal or on a market scale. The scarce studies of desire that have been reported in design research tend to focus on desirable product features or forms (e.g. Chang et al. 2006). The current focus is neither on behavioural consequences of nor on product features that elicit desire, but on the underlying conditions or antecedents.

Antecedents of desire

Arnold (1960) defines an emotion as the felt tendency toward anything intuitively appraised as beneficial or away from anything intuitively appraised as harmful. Desmet (2002) demonstrated that this definition is applicable to emotions experienced in the domain of product design. According to Frijda (1986) the points of reference in our appraisals are concerns: beneficial are those events that correspond, and harmful those that collide with concerns. The concern at stake can be a specific goal, an aspiration, a need, or a value. In his book, Frijda (1986, p. 283) explains desire as “engendered by the thought of, or encounter with, a fit object not in possession, and when such possession seems to call for.” A product is appraised as desirable when a person anticipates that possession will facilitate some concern realisation. The reported cases show a wide variety of concerns at stake, for example, the desire for success, for beauty, to entertain a particular lifestyle, to have rich experiences, and for balance in life. The examples also indicate that although there is always an element of anticipated concern realisation, the underlying eliciting conditions come in different shades. Three have been identified, hereafter referred to as desire of consequence, presence, and identity.

Desire of consequence

Products are instrumental in the sense that they are bought, owned, and used to serve some purpose in one’s life. We can desire for a product because we appraise that the product can serve such a purpose. The concern at stake can be a short term goal (e.g. I want to satisfy my thirst) and long term aspirations (e.g. I want to have a happy family life). The example cases

show that the anticipated use or consequences of use can be strong emotional antecedents of desire. Sixteen participants reported cases that fit this appraisal pattern. Reported goals are, for example: “I want to be sexy;” garment “to have fun;” kangaroo bal, and “to be sociable;” mobile phone. In all these cases the participants construe the product as *promising* for fulfilling that particular goal or need. One participant, for example reported that she desired for a particular ice-cream maker because she anticipated giving her ice-cream loving husband a pleasant surprise. In that case the desire represented the anticipated concern realisation of making her spouse happy. Another participant reported that “I desire for this backpack because it has exactly those features that I need; the size, the number of pockets, the material, and even the colours fit my idea of travelling. I can already see myself wearing this backpack next summer vacation.” This case illustrates that possession does not necessarily refer to some anticipated consequence of (using) the product, but can also refer to some anticipated event associated with the product.

Desire of presence

We saw that for desire of consequence, concern realisation is anticipated but not yet realised. In ten reported examples of desire the appraised fit seems to be more immediate. For example, one person reported to experience desire for her agenda: “whenever I hold my agenda I feel desire because of leather material that is very soft and has a lovely touch.” This desire can not be explained with an anticipated consequence of the product because the person already owns it. Moreover, she specifically reports that the desire is experienced while holding the agenda. Frijda (1986) argues that sometimes inherently pleasant stimuli (such as bright colours and sweet tastes) can elicit desire. This desire ‘for beauty’ is what some researchers would typify as ‘aesthetic desire’ (see, for example, Lazarus 1991). Products can bring us sensory pleasure that is desirable in itself. In those cases, the possession that is called for is independent of anticipated consequences other than the experience of sensory pleasure that was already present before the possession. Following this line of thought, possession of the product is called for because that will ensure continuation of experienced sensory pleasure. In these cases possession is exhibited in the product’s presence.

Desire of identity

Some examples of desirable products are difficult to explain with the above described eliciting conditions. These are cases that resemble the ‘social desire’ we sometimes experience towards people we admire (or are jealous of). In those cases we do not desire for

any consequence of 'owning' or interacting with that person, but in a sense desire to be that person (or to have his or her admirable characteristic). Something similar seems to be the case in five of the reported examples. One person explained his desire for a particular car model as follows: "This car represents something I strongly desire because it expresses powerful and at the same time gentleness. When I look at that car I somehow wish I could be just like it." In this and similar cases, not the sensory quality or the anticipated consequences of the product but the product's identity or character is the object of desire. Apparently the desire for an identity can be elicited by products in a similar way as we can desire for some social identity. Cupchik (1999) proposed that "an object can be seen by the user to resonate with and be symbolic of self." This idea matches the research of Belk (1988), who argued that we establish our identity through the products we surround ourselves with. Possession is called for because 'we are the sum of what we call ours,' and possession is manifested in identification.

General discussion

Inspiration and desire are subtle events, and therefore this discussion is intended to be part of an ongoing dialogue rather than a definitive statement. The intention of this paper was to provide a meaningful structure, and not to homogenize the body of material on inspiration and desire to some overly reduced core. Because the diversity of descriptions is as rich and significant as is the commonality in the experience, narrative descriptions have been included to reflect diversity. We saw that products elicit desire when appraised as 'a fit object not in possession, and when possession seems to call for.' The cases showed that although this definition implies that one can only desire for products that are not in possession, possession should be seen in a broad way, not only referring to ownership but also to any user-product interaction facilitated by ownership. We can desire to own, use, keep, touch, taste, and even, in a sense, to be a product or something associated with the product. In that sense, there seems to be no conceptual motive for distinguishing product desire from desire we experience in the context of human relationships. With respect to inspire, we saw that product inspiration always comes with a sense of connection and illumination that can manifest in various ways, but somehow always lift the person to a realm that goes beyond the everyday world of thoughts. Besides their singularities, the eliciting conditions of the two emotions also share similarities. The students in the design workshop experienced that designing for desire involves considerations that are comparable to those involved in designing for inspiration. It

is difficult to design a product that is desirable yet not inspiring, or the other way around. Although these emotions are different in terms of experience, they both involve motivation and their eliciting conditions involve aspirations and a sense of necessity. In a way, it does not seem too farfetched to assume that those products that inspire us are also those that we desire for. However, we prefer not to accentuate this because the differences between these emotions are at least as interesting as their similarities. Although our discussion may only touch on the surface of emotional complexity, in acknowledging these differences we aim to at least recognize the depths of that complexity. The differences are evident in action tendencies associated with these two emotions. An emotion always implies and involves an action tendency: a “readiness to engage in or disengage from interaction with some goal object in some particular fashion” (Frijda, Kuipers and Schure, 1989, p. 213), like moving towards, moving away, and moving against. These tendencies are relevant because they characterise experience and differentiate it from mere feelings of pleasantness or unpleasantness; different actions tendencies are what characterize different emotions (see Arnold, 1960). The action tendency involved in the experience of desire seems apparent: a tendency to approach, which can be typified as a pull towards the object. This tendency can be seen in the act of focussing on, buying, interacting with, or keeping hold of a product. Inspiration comes with a less palpable action tendency. From the cases it was observed that inspiration does not require a similar pull to the object as in product desire. If any tendency can be identified, it is a ‘push’ rather than a ‘pull’: as an uplifting experience inspiration pushes the person to a heightened state of awareness or towards some new (or rediscovered) thought or action. Besides the difference in pull versus push action tendencies, these two, and other pleasant emotions, involve the appraised (possibility) for concern realisation. The concern realisation elicits a pleasant emotion, and the particular appraisal characteristics and associated action tendencies establish what specific emotion is experienced.

Acknowledgements

The author acknowledges Erdem Demir for his contribution in the search for conceptual clarity. The enthusiastic students who volunteered to participate in the ‘inspire & desire’ workshop are acknowledged for their dedication and inspirational discussion.

References

- Arieti, S. (1976). *Creativity: the magic synthesis*. New York: Basic Books.
- Arnold, M.B. (1960). *Emotions and personality: vol. 1. Psychological aspects*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Belk, R.W. (1988). "Possessions and the extended self." *Journal of Consumer Research*, 15, 139-168.
- Chang, H.C., Lai, H.H. and Chang, Y.M. (2006). "Expression modes used by consumers in conveying desire for product form: a case study of a car." *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, 36, 3-10.
- Cupchik, G.C. (1999). "Emotion and industrial design: reconciling meanings and feelings." In C.J. Overbeeke and P. Hekkert (eds.) *Proceedings of the international conference on design and emotion*. Delft: Delft University of Technology, 75-82.
- Desmet, P.M.A. (2002). *Designing Emotions*. Unpublished doctoral thesis. Available from URL: <<http://studiolab.io.tudelft.nl/desmet/publications>>. [Accessed 2005 March 20].
- Frijda, N.H. (1986). *The emotions*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- Frijda, N.H., Kuipers, P. and Schure, E. (1989). "Relations among emotion, appraisal, and emotional action readiness." *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 57, 212-228,
- Ger, G., Belk, R.W. and Lascu, D.L. (1993). "The development of consumer desire in marketizing and developing economies: the cases of Romania and Turkey." *Advances in Consumer Research*, 20, 102-107.
- Hart, T. (1998). "Inspiration: exploring the experience and its meaning." *Journal of Humanistic Psychology*, 38(3), 7-35.
- Lazarus, R.S. (1991). *Emotion and Adaptation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Lynn, M. and Harris, J. (1997). "The desire for unique consumer products: a new individual differences scale." *Psychology and Marketing*, 16(4), 601-616.
- May, R. (1975). *The courage to create*. New York: Bantam.
- Meister, R. (1996). "Beyond satisfaction: desire, consumption, and the future of socialism." *Topoi*, 15, 189-210.
- Williams, M.E. (1982). *Inspiration and Milton and Keats*. Totowa, NJ: Barnes and Nobles.